

ASSESSMENT OF FATIGUE DAMAGE ONSET AND GROWTH IN PLAIN WEAVE COMPOSITES WITH EMBEDDED FLAWS

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ABSTRACT

Due to the advantageous mechanical properties of textile composites such as high rigidity, strength to weight ratio, fracture toughness and damage tolerance, have made them recommended composites for designing load-bearing structures used in aerospace components. However, their damage behavior under fatigue loading is complex because of the anisotropic nature of the mechanical properties, the presence of flaws that can be induced during manufacturing and due to the interaction of many damage mechanisms created during their solicitation. The main objective of this study is to assess the influence of manufacturing flaws on the fatigue life of plain weave composites. Test coupons containing an artificial delamination were assessed in real time by using the Acoustic Emission (AE) techniques under tension-tension fatigue loading. The paper proposes an experimental approach, which use AE monitoring to generate S/N fatigue life threshold curves corresponding to the microscopic damage onset and to the propagation of the delamination around the embedded artificial flaw area. At a fixed fatigue cycling frequency (7 Hz) and stress ratio ($R=0.1$), two environmental conditions were adopted in order to estimate the influence of temperature exposure on the damage initiation and on fatigue life. Delamination growth area around the inserted flaw was localized by using AE zonal localization algorithm with the validation of ultrasonic C-scan imaging. A filtering method of AE data was developed to discriminate the signals generated by macroscopic delamination and microscopic damage associated with matrix cracking appearing within and at the edges of composite coupons. In parallel to this, correlations were made with previous experimental results on the evolution of macroscopic mechanical properties of the material during the cycling test by the use of digital image correlation (DIC) strain mapping technique.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing use of fabric composite materials has emphasized the necessity to comprehend their leading modes of failure under fatigue loading related to interface damage and macroscopic delamination. For safe use of such materials, it's necessary to implement experimental approaches, analytical and numerical modeling tools to help predicting fatigue life under dynamic loading. Thus, detail knowledge about their behavior should be based upon an understanding of their damage mechanism's development at the microscopic scale. It is well known, that the presence of damage created under loading induces an alteration of mechanical performance of the structure. In addition, plain weave composites may include a different type of fabrication flaws able to generate early failures under fatigue loading. The presence of such flaws affects the long-term reliability of the composite structure in terms of life duration, residual strength, stiffness and structure safety.

However, damage development in plain weave composites, especially under fatigue loading, is difficult to analyze because of the interconnection of fabric strands [1] and also due to shear stresses created between wraps and weft fibers, which made the damage accumulation in plain weave composites even more complicated and not fully understood. Lately, a review of the advances in

fatigue insight realized by Wicaksono [2], have shown that the early stage damages that occur in woven composites under fatigue loading are normally associated to matrix micro cracking, fiber/matrix interface debonding followed, in later fatigue stages, by macroscopic damage mechanisms related mainly to delamination between fill and warp and delamination between adjacent layers. In general, fatigue damage spreads with applied load cycles as accumulative damage mechanism and dissimilar types of damage may interact concurrently [2]. Due to cumulative damage and disperse nature of cracks occurring in fabric composites, the prediction of fatigue life of composite structures subjected to cyclic loading remains a serious difficulty for composite designers. Therefore, there is a requisite to develop modeling methods combined with experimental damage monitoring techniques to have a thorough understanding of the initiation of cracks and propagation of interlaminar damage mechanism generated during fatigue loading of the composite.

This study proposes the use damage monitoring methods to generate fatigue life curves, which will be used to predict the delamination onset in plain weave composites. The main objective is to exploit acoustic emission stress wave data to detect initiation of emerging damage in the composite under loading. As mentioned in several works the acoustic emission can distinguish between fatigue damage mechanisms in composites [3-7]. In this work, damage monitoring by acoustic emission will provide fatigue life threshold curves associated with damage initiation in composite coupons, related to the matrix cracking and delamination propagation, which is induced by the presence of artificial flaws. Delamination growth area around the inserted flaw was localized by using AE zonal localization algorithm, which employs a first hit algorithm to locate the events originating from the damaged area around the embedded artificial flaw. This monitoring approach will help accurately distinguish a delamination growth area in terms of spatial location of the delamination area.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Material and mechanical testing

The composite material used is a quasi-isotropic plain weave (0/90) carbon/epoxy laminate prepared as a 8 plies laminates of stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_S$, with coupon dimensions of 304.8 x 76.2 x 1.62 mm³. An artificial flaw is inserted in the manufactured coupons, by embedding a centered 12.7 x 12.7 mm² Teflon tape between the third and the fourth layers as shown in figure 1.

The samples were subjected to a simple cyclic loading spectrum with continuous AE monitoring as represented by figure 2. All mechanical tests were carried out on an MTS 100 kN servo-Hydraulic testing machine under load-controlled mode. The load was transferred to the specimen through hydraulic grips, which maintained a constant pressure of 16 MPa at each extremity (figure 3). To evaluate the effect of high temperature exposure on delamination onset, 10 specimens were exposed to isothermal mechanical testing at 7 Hz frequency with high temperature exposure at 120 °C with damage monitoring by AE technique. The number of tested coupons for all experiments is listed in table 1. Fatigue loading levels were chosen by performing quasi-static tests monitored by AE at room temperature tests. The objective was to determine the ultimate tensile load and the lowest loading level required to initiate damage. Fatigue loading levels were then chosen based on the results of these tests. Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted under constant sinusoidal cycles at loading frequency of 7 Hz with stress ratio R of 0.1.

Figure 1: Dimension of the samples and position of the sensors around the embedded flaw

Figure 2: Testing protocol for 7 Hz room and high temperature tests

Table 1: Number of coupons and loading levels details for temperature fatigue tests

Type of tests	Number of tested coupons	Loading levels in percentage of UTL
7 Hz fatigue tests at room temperature	17	53% / 59% / 65% / 71%
7 Hz fatigue tests at high temperature 120°C	10	50% / 55% / 60%

2.2 Acoustic emission procedures for damage monitoring

The acoustic emission data acquisition system used in the experiments is provided by Mistras group. Two types of piezoelectric sensors were used in the tests. The first used miniature piezoelectric sensor HD2WD has a large frequency band between 330 kHz and 1.8 MHz and it is named sensor 1. Sensor 2 is the WD piezoelectric sensor characterised by a large frequency response band up to 1 MHz which have a maximum sensitivity between 125 kHz and 450 kHz. Each sensor is connected to a preamplifier that transmits analogic signals to an eight-channel acquisition and treatment unit μ DISP. The AE signals data are therefore gathered and stored digitally on a computer via a PCI connection bus using *AEWin* software. The signal processing, feature extraction, data management and manipulation are performed by *AEWin* Post software. After each test, the AE signals were further analysed using Noesis Software from Envirocoustics. Two AE monitoring configuration were used. The first one used a simple configuration of the two distinct acoustic sensors mentioned above. The two PZT sensors were positioned at the same distance from the embedded flaw location (figure 1) and attached on the specimen using fasteners made of aluminum and rubber as a fixture system and acoustically coupled with vacuum grease. The second configuration uses four WD sensors as shown by figure 3. This configuration allows using the 2D anisotropic location algorithm provided with the AE apparatus. The algorithm identifies a predefined zone as the damage location and performs TOA computation according to the first triggered sensor.

To perform AE location tests, group velocity in both directions was taken around 5000 m/s because the tested composite is quasi-isotropic. The velocity was also estimated by pencil break tests and verified with Laser Doppler Vibrometer [8], which was used to generate lamb wave dispersion curves for the material. The AE detection threshold was chosen equal to 75 dB for fatigue tests. Increasing the threshold value intended to reduce the noise caused by the MTS machine during dynamic testing. Otherwise, the selected sampling rate was 5 MHz and the system timing parameters were set at 800 μ s for HDT (hit definition time), 200 μ s for PDT (peak definition time) and 1000 μ s for HLT (hit Lock-out time). A filtering interval between 100 kHz and 2 MHz was chosen. The same experimental conditions were adopted for all tests and putty was applied on the grips and around tabs in order to minimize mechanical vibration noise.

Figure 3: Position of WD sensors on the sample for AE zonal location

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 Generation of fatigue life curves for 7Hz under room temperature testing

Both unflawed and coupons with embedded flaws were submitted to preliminary quasi-static tension tests to determine the static strength of composites, and also to distinguish the applied stress levels from which the coupons generate acoustic emission waves. These stress values define the “Acoustic Emission threshold” indicating the onset of matrix and interface micro-failures in the laminate. The detailed results of static part of the testing were presented elsewhere [9]. The obtained cumulative AE count curves tend to increase exponentially with increasing static load, and follow a similar growth trend for all twelve coupons. However, the rate of curves growth was different for each coupon. A range of thresholds load corresponding to damage onset was identified for every tested coupon. In order to emphasize the AE signals that are associated with the fatigue propagation of embedded artificial delamination, feature data filtering procedure based on the signal duration and frequencies of AE signal was developed. The AE data filtering method helps to reduce the feature matrix of fatigue data by eliminating data associated with noise induced by fatigue crack opening and closing. In fact, the periodic rubbing between surfaces created by edge delamination during cycling, can generate repetitive AE emissions that are not associated with real damage. Also, such data filtering method allows deciphering between AE events that are mostly associated with the matrix micro cracking and macroscopic delamination. The data processing methods was helpful to generate fatigue life S/N curves that characterize the onset of macroscopic delamination in the coupons. It has been concluded by several investigators [10-13] that failures associated with delamination and interface damage in carbon-fiber composite generate modal AE waveforms characterized by large durations and intermediate frequency range. AE signals

Figure 4: AE data selection for macroscopic damage identification: waveforms and AE feature data filtering approaches

generated by the matrix micro cracks have generally short time durations and low frequency contents unlike fiber breakage signals, which are characterized by short duration, high energy and the modal spectra have high-frequency range. The adopted signal processing and filtering method was established on selecting AE signals with large duration and comprised in a frequency interval of 100 kHz to 450 kHz. Figure 4-a shows the values of large duration peaks related to macroscopic damage mechanisms such as interlaminar delaminations. Figure 4-b shows the distribution plot of AE signal durations versus time, only AE signals whose duration is greater than 100 μs and frequency content is within the interval [100 kHz- 450 kHz] were kept for data analysis.. The data feature filtering approach was applied for all recorded AE data. Thanks to the use of AE feature filtering, damage onset and delamination onset thresholds have been identified and served to generate fatigue life S/N curves. By extracting the duration peaks for every tested coupon as illustrated by figure 4, it was possible to generate S/N curves based on log-linear straight-line assumption by fitting the experimental points. The models were found by using the following analytical expression:

(a)

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{UTS}} = a + b \log (N) \quad (1)$$

where, a and b are the intercept and the slope of the curve. Many models could be derived by using this filtering method in order to bring out different stage of fatigue damage evolution of the tested coupons.

Figure 5 – S/N fatigue life damage onset obtained by AE monitoring and localization data for 7Hz and room temperature test case

Predictive fatigue models were derived as shown by figure 5. The S-N curve denoted by P1 represents the AE fatigue life thresholds identified at 9% of fatigue life ratio N/N_f , obtained by performing cycling tests on nine coupons at 53%, 59%, 65% and 71% of the ultimate tensile load. The P1 fatigue curve is correlated with matrix intra-yarn cracks appearing essentially in 90° yarns and also with interplay delamination created at the free edges of the coupons. The S-N curve denoted by P2 (50% of fatigue life ratio N/N_f), represents the fatigue life curve which was associated with the macroscopic delamination onset generated by an inserted artificial flaw [9]. These results were confirmed by ultrasonic C-scan imaging performed on some selected coupons. Figure 6 shows an example of damages growth around the embedded flaw obtained by zonal planar localization AE

sources during fatigue loading. The original localization results generated by AEwin software display the coordinates of the detected damage positions by small red dots (figure 6-a). However, for more accurate determination of damage areas with high localization density, it is important to know when the number of dots per unit of surface becomes relevant. Therefore a density function analysis was applied to the preliminary location AE data results obtained by using AEwin localization software. To enhance the visualization of the delaminated area in the composite, density plots of the detected AE signals were computed and presented on a visual map as shown in figure 6-b. DensityVille algorithm [14] based on Gaussian weighting function was used to compute local density plots at a precise position.

Figure 6: Damage area localization results for the coupon fatigue loaded of 60% of the fatigue life: a) AE data computed by zonal localization algorithm, b) Density plots visualization, c) C-Scan imaging.

Figure 7: AE localization Density diagrams of fatigue damage obtained at different stage of fatigue loading for coupon loaded at 65 % of UTL under 7Hz.

A high value of localization density indicates a high number of localization dots cumulated in a specified region. Therefore, the fatigue damage onset around the artificial flaw is determined at the time when a fixed high value of localization density appears near or on the flaw. Figure 7 shows an example of density diagrams of fatigue damage observed at different stage of fatigue loading for the coupon loaded at 65 % of UTL under 7Hz. This figure shows clearly that damage arises around the embedded artificial flaw and extends gradually as the number of cycle increases. The used red color-coding reflects areas of high localization density. The obtained S/N curve associated to the delamination onset obtained by using zonal localization technique was shown by figure 5 and is represented by line denoted by L. The prediction model represented by the L curve was determined by the use of only three experimental data, these points correspond to lifetimes obtained by achieving three fatigue tests carried out at different loadings. The result is encouraging, but insufficient; more test results are required to establish a more reliable predictive model. However, the obtained curve is just after the S/N curve which corresponds to the initiation of the matrix microcracking and immediately before the S/N curve obtained at 50% of fatigue life ratio N/N_f of the composite. At this ratio of fatigue life, the composite shows a pronounced drop in the stiffness ratio[15]. Earlier results obtained by combining AE monitoring and DIC strain mapping have demonstrated that the delamination, associated with an artificial flaws, starts to extend at about 50% of N/N_f [15]. It can be noticed from figure 5 that, for high loading stress; the flaw damage onset threshold was close to P1 model associated with matrix cracking appearance in the flawed region. However, for 53% loading level, the data point of 2D anisotropic localization model becomes distant from the P1 model and closer to the 60% of fatigue life. As said, due to a limited number of samples tested, it was difficult to conclude on the validity of the obtained predictive model developed by AE localization. Nevertheless, the prognostic line model obtained by localization technique gives a good indication of the threshold from which damage starts to grow around the flaw and develops until becoming a macroscopic delamination.

2.1 Generation of fatigue life curves for 7Hz under high temperature testing (120°C)

The purpose of this part was to investigate the effect of thermal degradation of the matrix and fiber/matrix interface on the fatigue life onset of delamination. The thermal degradation is induced by exposing the composite to isothermal high temperature during mechanical loading. It's well known that the combined effect of environmental and mechanical degradation tends to shorten the fatigue life of composites compared to those that have not been environmentally exposed.

Ten coupons were used to perform high-temperature fatigue tests under cycling frequency of 7 Hz in dry environment. Ultimate static tensile load was found to be normally lower in a 120°C dry environment than in the room temperature one. Tension-tension fatigue testing was done for 53%, 59%, 65% and 71% of the ultimate tensile load obtained by static testing at 120°C. The tests were stopped before final failure when an increase of 5 % of the strain is reached. The strain measurements were performed employing a non-contact strain measurement done by using a high-speed video-extensometer. The AE signal processing technique and the location setup were kept the same as the fatigue tests done under room temperature. Figure 8, presents the S/N curves results obtained for both cases of fatigue tests conducted under high temperature and ambient temperature conditions. For each case study, the figure plots the S/N fatigue curves associated with the initiation of matrix cracking, and the propagation of macroscopic delamination obtained by AE zonal location method. The comparison of S /N curves shown in figure 8 displays that the composite samples having undergone fatigue tests at a 120°C temperature were seriously affected by temperature exposure. To achieve the comparison shown in figure 8, stress data were reduced dividing the maximum stress by the ultimate static tensile stress obtained at room temperature. The figure 8, shows that fatigue lives are significantly lower for the specimen exposed at high temperature than for unexposed specimens. In summary, the obtained results show clearly that the fatigue loading under high-temperature accelerates significantly the process of degradation of the matrix and the interphase fiber/matrix,

Figure 8: S/N fatigue life damage onset obtained by AE monitoring and localization data for samples tested under 7Hz at room temperature and at 120^oC.

which is weakening the composite toughness and promotes early damage of the matrix and the fiber/ matrix interface and contribute to the rapid spread of delamination around the artificial flaw.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This paper develops an experimental approach based on acoustic emission to generate fatigue life curves and to predict the onset of fatigue damage in plain weave carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic composites. The tested samples contain a Teflon insert that simulates the presence of a manufacturing flaw. Acoustic emission was used to monitor the damage evolution during tension-tension fatigue testing. A filtering method of the AE data features was performed in order to generate delamination onset S/N curves. The following conclusions were reached:

- Acoustic emission monitoring is a powerful technique to determine the number of cycle at which damage initiate in the plain weave composite under fatigue loading. By using AE data fatigue life S/N curves damage onset were generated for matrix cracking and for macroscopic delamination.
- A filtering procedures based on the signal time duration and frequency band was developed to generate fatigue life S/N curve associated with the propagation of an embedded artificial delamination. A localization technique was developed to localize delamination area growth under fatigue loading.
- The first stage of damage that appears during the cycling of the composite is matrix cracking and edge delamination followed by macroscopic delamination in the flaw zone.
- Fatigue loading under high-temperature accelerates significantly the process of degradation of the composite and promotes early damage of the matrix and the fibre / matrix interface and contribute to the rapid spread of delamination around the artificial flaw.

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